

Life Science Competence Centres: Open by Design

Submission in progress

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Keywords: open science, life sciences, research infrastructures, EOSC, services, data steward, skills network, data management, FAIR, knowledge transfer, science implementation, capacity building, competence centres, OSCARS

Abstract

The European Research Area (ERA) includes five Science Clusters, collaborative groups of research infrastructures (RIs) organised around specific thematic areas. Life Science RIs (LS-RIs), individually, and collectively as the LS-RI cluster, provide the LS community with access to cutting-edge technologies. They also contribute to the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), under the aegis of the EOSC Federation. They are currently actively involved in the design and implementation of Competence Centres (CCs). These aim to increase the accessibility of domain-specific knowledge and tools, enhance interoperability, facilitate sharing and harmonisation of procedures, and promote Open Science and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) practices. In this paper, we report a landscape mapping of the existing resources that form the basis for the construction of CCs. We describe the possible design of CCs and their articulation with the LS-RIs. We focus on community-based ideas and recommendations to increase the potential of CCs to address long-standing challenges in sustainability, governance, scalability, and interoperability of Open Science within the EOSC and the ERA more generally.

When fully implemented, the LS CCs will serve as dynamic hubs to foster innovation, contribute to the EOSC's future web of FAIR data and services, and support ongoing development of the EOSC Federation. They will act as drivers of collaborative and impactful LS research in Europe and beyond. We explore the underlying challenges, and propose solutions, to ensure that the establishment of CCs will add value to the LS-RI community, and to the EOSC, in a sustainable way.

Introduction

Research Infrastructures (RIs)

European Research Infrastructures (RIs) are state-of-the-art facilities helping the European and global scientific community to conduct top-tier research in various fields. These European RIs exist at single sites, as distributed networks, or virtually, and cover different specific scientific domains. They provide a wide portfolio of technologies and methodologies, data and computing resources, knowledge-based resources, such as archives and collections, as well as training resources and expert community groups. They promote innovation through collaborations with Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), and joint activities in large European initiatives, such as those supported under Horizon Europe. Through interdisciplinary collaborations - including partnerships with the private sector - RIs continually expand their expertise to tackle pressing global challenges. In the Life Sciences, for example, large-scale RI consortia provide critical support for research on infectious diseases (e.g. [ISIDORE](#)), cancer (e.g. [CanSERV](#), [EUCAIM](#)), and agroecology ([AgroServ](#)), as well as the development of next generation technologies and scientific services (e.g. [EVERSE](#), [Fragment-Screen](#), [IMAGINE](#)).

At the global level, European RIs are positioned as pivotal elements of international scientific collaboration as part of the [Open Science and Open Access framework](#). They enhance Europe's competitiveness in science and technology innovation, and also foster international cooperation through democratising access to their resources, enabling scientists in Europe and worldwide to tackle grand challenges and develop solutions together. The excellence and accessibility of European RIs, with their high quality standards, attract researchers from many domains, contributing to making the European Research Area (ERA) a hub for high-impact science.

The RI Landscape in Europe: The ESFRI Roadmap

The RI landscape in Europe is mainly structured around the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures ([ESFRI](#)) [roadmap](#). Established in 2002 by the European Union (EU) Council, ESFRI promotes a rational approach to the development of RIs across Europe. The ESFRI regularly assesses and updates its roadmap, which identifies key RI landmarks and projects, complementing

the Member States' own national roadmaps. Typically, a set of services, in a defined thematic or methodological area, will initially be supported by one or more rounds of short-term national and/or EU funding, to demonstrate utility to the research community. As a single example, the European Virus Archive (EVA) was funded as a project by the EU Seventh Framework Programme from 2009 to 2014, then, as the Horizon 2020 projects [European Virus Archive goes global](#) (2015-2019) and [European Virus Archive is Global](#) (2020-2024), before arriving at sufficient operational maturity to become a candidate for inclusion on the ESFRI roadmap. This ensures that European RIs continue to serve the needs of the LS research community and are prompt to respond to and align with the evolving needs of the ERA, supporting European leadership across various scientific fields.

Life Sciences Research Infrastructures (LS-RIs) within the ESFRI Roadmap

The ESFRI roadmap is divided into six large thematic categories, Data, Computing & Digital RIs; Energy; Environment; Physical Sciences & Engineering; Social Sciences & Humanities; and Health & Food. For historical reasons, the RIs that fall into the latter describe themselves as the “Life Science” RIs ([LS-RIs](#)). The 15 ESFRI landmarks that currently make up the LS-RI group are distinguished by their heterogeneity of scale, focus and organisation. Despite this, they have a tradition of undertaking cross-cutting initiatives, both in service provision to experimental scientists, and with regards to digital resources and expertise. A prominent example of the latter was the recent [By-COVID](#) project that united 10 of the LS-RIs as part of the EU's response to the pandemic caused by SARS-CoV-2.

EOSC

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is an initiative launched in 2015 by the European Commission (EC) and European Member States (including Associated Countries). It is considered to be an essential building block of the European e-infrastructure ecosystem, key not only to Data, Computing & Digital RIs within ESFRI, but to EU research more broadly. It aims to promote Open Science practices (Appleton *et al.*, 2020) through the creation of a web of FAIR data and services, promoting the generalised adoption of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) practices (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016, Jacobsen *et al.*, 2020). EOSC is a transformative initiative involving a wide range of stakeholders, set to support the entire research lifecycle, from planning, through execution, to dissemination of results. It aims to create a unified and open environment for data and research resources across all disciplines, facilitating access to a wide array of data, tools, and services for researchers, enabling collaborative and data-driven science.

The EOSC vision is being implemented in a digital ecosystem where scientists can store, share, and reuse research data across borders and disciplines. By providing a federated system that connects researchers, research organisations, and institutions, EOSC enhances the efficiency and productivity of European research, at the individual and RI level. This integration fosters innovation and accelerates scientific discovery by making it easier for researchers to access and exploit the information they need. Importantly, EOSC involves a wide range of other stakeholders, including industry, and policymakers, ensuring its relevance for both research and innovation.

EOSC is a cross-border open innovation environment for FAIR data management and analytical services, respecting the CARE (Collective Benefits, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics) principles (Dalley *et al.*, 2008; Carroll *et al.*, 2020) and attentive to digital security, thereby contributing to the sustainability of ESFRI and pan-European RIs.

[Science Clusters \(SCs\)](#)

One of the key goals of EOSC is to break down silos and enhance interdisciplinary research by enabling access to integrated datasets, providing cloud-interoperability tools and computational resources from different domains through the organisation of RIs into Science Clusters (SCs). In contrast to the ESFRI categories listed above, these are more operational federations of RIs in a particular domain. To align the EOSC with ESFRI objectives, five EOSC SC projects were launched in 2019, adopting a "system of systems" framework (Gotz *et al.*, 2020): [ENVRI-FAIR](#) (environmental sciences); [ESCAPE](#) (astronomy, astroparticle and particle physics); [PaNOSC](#) (photon and neutron

sciences); [SSHOC](#) (social sciences and humanities); and [EOSC-Life](#) (life sciences) that brought together 13 of the LS-RIs to create an open, digital and collaborative space for biological and medical research. Synergies between SCs enhance researchers' efficiency and productivity through common open-science standards and shared services (Petzold *et al.*, 2024). Collectively, they have played a significant role in structuring part of the EOSC research environment (Lamanna *et al.*, 2021).

The 5 EOSC SC projects leveraged existing interactions and facilitated new and innovative, inter-cluster and cross-domain collaborations and projects among RIs. While each SC focused on domain-specific needs for integrating its data assets into EOSC, all SCs also prioritised interoperability and harmonisation across domains, in line with the EOSC Interoperability Framework (David *et al.*, 2023a, Nyberg Åkerström *et al.*, 2024). The projects enhanced accessibility and use of data, tools, resources, and training, and promoted FAIR data management practices. For the LS SC, an online [catalogue of sustainable outcomes from EOSC-Life](#) was produced. Moving forward, more work is required to amplify, scale and sustain these efforts.

A step towards that amplification and sustainability was provided through the establishment of the OSCARS project (Nentwich *et al.*, 2025). It builds on the SC approach to ensure the discoverability, access and integration of SC and RI services (Figure 1; see Table 1 for more details of the ESFRI LS-RIs) in EOSC for the research communities, with two main objectives:

i) showcasing and testing the utilisation of EOSC resources by various research communities through collaborative Open Science projects and services spanning domains. Details of these initiatives can be found on the [OSCARS website](#), and will not be described further here.

ii) increasing the level of understanding and application of EOSC methodologies across the RI communities within the five European SCs. This involves supporting the maintenance of adaptable EOSC services in these clusters, as well as backing community-driven efforts to promote alignment and interoperability with EOSC standards, therefore broadening engagement with all user communities.

Figure 1: The landscape of Life Science Research Infrastructures (LS-RIs) and the broader scientific domain ecosystem. The top section highlights various entities and services (Table 1 & Supplementary Material 1) within the LS-RI landscape. European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs, a subset of the LS-RIs, see Glossary in Supplementary Material 2) and other RIs equate to facilities, tools, platforms, training resources, expert groups, virtual centres, cloud computing resources, and databases. These elements align with key themes and goals such as health and food, combating diseases, ecosystems, basic research, and driving innovation. The middle section focuses on the evolving landscape of LS-RIs, emphasising diverse thematics and methodologies within the LS domain. The bottom section presents the connection of LS-RIs to other SCs, showcasing the collaborative role of the five EOSC SC projects in co-creating the EOSC and demonstrating the multidisciplinary collaboration in the OSCARS project.

Table 1: Research services and resources provided by ESFRI LS-RIs which participated in a mapping survey through the OSCARS project, categorised into data & databases, technologies and facilities, computational tools, expertise & support, and materials. A version with more stakeholders beyond LS-RI is available in Supplementary Material 1.

ESFRI LS-RIs	DOMAIN / COMPETENCE	SERVICES & RESOURCES TO DATE	URL
*EOSC-Life partner		Data & Databases, Technologies & Facilities, Computational Tools, Expertise & Support, Materials	
BBMRI-ERIC *	BIOBANKING & BIOMOLECULAR RESOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biobank samples and data services • Interoperability, traceability support • Quality management & ELSI services • Biobanking service support • Training 	https://www.bbMRI-eric.eu/bbMRI-sample-and-data-portal/ https://www.bbMRI-eric.eu/howtomiabis/ https://www.bbMRI-eric.eu/services/quality-management/ https://www.bbMRI-eric.eu/services-support/ https://www.bbMRI-eric.eu/services/e-learning/
EATRIS-ERIC *	TRANSLATIONAL MEDICINE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translational medicine technologies and facilities • Expert centres • Innovation management expertise • Self-service translational medicine resources • Training (TRANSMED Academy) 	https://eatris.eu/infrastructure/product-platforms/ https://eatris.eu/eatris-expert-centres/ https://eatris.eu/innovation-services/ https://eatris.eu/self-service-resources/ https://eatris.eu/transmed-academy/
ECRIN *	CLINICAL TRIALS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical trials services • Clinical trials tools • Training 	https://ecrin.org/clinical-trials https://ecrin.org/tools https://ecrin.org/training
ELIXIR *	CURATED DATABASES & BIOINFORMATICS SERVICES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deposition databases • Data curation services, guidelines • Interoperability services and support • Training & training database 	https://elixir-europe.org/services https://elixir-europe.org/platforms Catalogues include resources hosted across the ELIXIR Nodes (including EMBL-EBI)
EMBRC-ERIC *	MARINE BIOLOGY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine biology technologies & services • Data analysis services • Marine biological resources • Training 	https://www.embrc.eu/services https://trace-embrc.eu/ https://www.marinetraining.eu/home
EMPHASIS *	PLANT PHENOTYPING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plant phenotyping services • Data services • Training 	https://emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu/services https://emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu/services/emphasis-pilots
ERINHA *	HIGHLY PATHOGENIC MICROORGANISMS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to high containment facilities • Biosafety and Biosecurity Expertise • Training 	https://erinha.eu/access-our-services/scientific-services/ https://erinha.eu/erinha-scientific-strategy/unique-facilities-and-scientists/ https://erinha.eu/access-our-services/training/
EU-OPENSREEN ERIC *	CHEMICAL BIOLOGY & DRUG DISCOVERY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chem. Bio. & Med. Chem. services • Chem. Bio. compound collections • Chemical biology database (ECBD) • Training 	https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/services https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/services/training
EURO-BIOIMAGING ERIC *	BIOLOGICAL & BIOMEDICAL IMAGING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Imaging technologies & services • Image analysis services (bioimage desktop) • FAIR data services & support • Training 	https://www.eurobioimaging-access.eu/service https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/data-services/ https://band.vm.fedcloud.eu/#/eosc-landingpage https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/training/
IBISBA	BIOMANUFACTURING SERVICES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biomanufacturing services • FAIR data services & support • Training 	https://ibisba.eu/one-stop-shop/ https://hub.ibisba.eu/
INFRAFRONTIER ERIC *	DISEASE MODELS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disease models services • Mutant models repository and FAIR data resource (EMMA) • Training 	https://infrafrontier.eu/services/ https://www.infrafrontier.eu/emma/ https://infrafrontier.eu/training-events/
INSTRUCT-ERIC *	STRUCTURAL BIOLOGY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structural biology & analysis services • Training 	https://instruct-eric.org/platform-catalogue https://instruct-eric.org/training
MIRRI-ERIC *	MICROBIAL RESOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbial research services • Microbial resources (and data) • Training 	https://www.mirri.org/services/ https://www.mirri.org/microbial-resources-data/ https://www.mirri.org/training-education/
ANAEE-ERIC	ECOSYSTEMS ANALYSIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecosystem research & analysis services • Data and models portals 	https://www.anaee.eu/services https://www.anaee.eu/services/data-and-models-portals
CROSS-DOMAIN PLATFORMS & REGISTRIES		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> FAIRsharing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> LS-RI website <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EOSC platform 	https://fairsharing.org/ https://lifescience-ri.eu/html https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/

Competence Centres Facilitating Data-Intensive Research

The LS domain has rapidly transformed into an environment characterised by data-intensive research, enabled by the emergence of Big Data, with numerous examples in biology (Pal *et al.*, 2020), global health (Andreu-Perez *et al.*, 2015), diagnostics and therapeutics (Perakakis *et al.*, 2018), and personalised medicine (Cirillo and Valencia, 2019; Velmovitsky *et al.*, 2021). Advances in high-throughput technologies (D'Argenio, 2018), omics platforms (Perakakis *et al.*, 2018), biobanks (Akyüz *et al.*, 2024) and digital clinical records (Khennou *et al.*, 2018) now generate massive, complex datasets that require specialised tools and methods for integration and analysis (Filingier *et al.*, 2019). Traditionally, individual researchers or small research teams handled data curation and analysis. As data complexity increases and new technologies emerge, however, this decentralised approach is proving increasingly insufficient. This must also consider multi-modality since more and more studies are linked to other LS-adjacent environmental and earth science fields (Devictor and Bensaude-Vincent, 2016, Kamilaris *et al.*, 2017, Guidi *et al.*, 2020).

A key change is advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) (Shi *et al.*, 2024). AI-based tools, for instance used for protein design (Laveglia *et al.*, 2022), clinical diagnosis or drug development are transforming the way data can be interpreted and applied. These technologies rely on well-structured, interoperable, and high-quality datasets. The acceleration of AI in LS is also fuelled by the expanding availability of large datasets, necessitating a better understanding of their quality with sufficient and appropriate metadata, especially in terms of AI readiness.

Nonetheless, with technological progress driving down costs and helping researchers deal with the increasing complexity of data generated, AI-ready data is becoming more accessible. This growing opportunity brings with it new challenges. Data must be curated according to FAIR principles, must have a clear provenance, be of a defined quality (Wittner *et al.*, 2022), and made usable across contexts. RIs have both the vocation and expertise to contribute to this process, but acting in isolation wastes resources and limits their potential impact. For instance, the BioImage Archive community has developed a set of recommendations to ensure standardisation and reusability of image data (Zulueta-Coarasa *et al.*, 2025). Another example is the BioImage Model Zoo (Ouyang *et al.*, 2022), offering a collection of FAIR AI models that are openly available and described with metadata specifications that enable interoperability across a range of image analysis tools. This interoperability is enhanced by broader community efforts like the Research Data Alliance [FAIR4ML](#) Interest Group, which is working to ensure that AI models are described in a standardised way across disciplines. Further, integrating data and services across RIs, for instance linking multi-modal datasets across health, environmental and social sciences, can create novel and interdisciplinary resources for research and innovation (e.g. David *et al.*, 2015, Croset *et al.*, 2015, David *et al.*, 2017, Machicao *et al.*, 2022, [Adaptive Platform Trial Tools | Ecrin](#)).

Competence Centres (CCs) are emerging as a potential mechanism to support changes in the way data - but also related best practices and expertise - are handled, adapted, and exploited across contexts and disciplines. CCs provide a common ground for RIs to align efforts, share best practices, and enable researchers to access interoperable, AI-ready, FAIR and Open resources without needing advanced technical expertise. By providing expertise, and coordinating tools and standards, CCs can ensure that the broader scientific community can benefit from these new, data-driven LS approaches, fostering innovation at scale.

Competence Centres

Establishing Competence Centres (CCs) was deemed the most efficient way to achieve the second objective given above, of facilitating a common understanding and harmonised application of EOSC methodologies across RIs. The CCs would be a solution to address long-standing challenges in accessibility, interoperability, and sustainability. In the current context, we use the term with a specific meaning (Definition 1). Through their vocation to be "one-stop-shops" for researchers, foster collaboration, training, and exchange of knowledge, CCs can build bridges between RIs and help align their activities with broader Open Science and EOSC goals.

Definition 1: Competence Centre (CC)

A CC is a single point of reference for finding and accessing training programmes, educational materials, best practices, and tools, that i) raises awareness, ii) disseminates information, and iii) provides explanations and advice, covering a geographical area, or a specific methodological or thematic domain. CCs support the implementation, management, reuse, sharing and analysis of FAIR data and other digital research objects.

A core purpose of CCs is to promulgate FAIR principles and Open Science practices. By building frameworks and support mechanisms, CCs should ensure these practices become widespread and deeply embedded in scientific research processes. They should also help address the critical challenge of promoting interoperability across RIs and domains.

LS-RIs Competence Centres - current concepts, missions, and perspectives

Current Concepts for CCs among the LS-RIs

In order to improve the discoverability and accessibility of existing services and expertise, under the impulsion of the EOSC Federation, and particularly within the context of the OSCARS project (Bodera Sempere *et al.*, 2024, Chambers *et al.*, 2024 and Hienola *et al.*, 2024), staff from different LS-related research organisations have begun - following the radical collaboration method applied by Pickering *et al.* (2021) - to describe specific CCs that could be integrated into a coherent, user-oriented system for resource discovery and access. By harmonising access mechanisms, for example through a unified Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) service, the [Life Science AAI](#), and promoting composability and interoperability, LS CCs are expected to increase the usability of services, resources, and expertise in the LS domain while fostering collaboration.

In practical terms, they will most likely be virtual, even if in the future they could operate as separate legal entities. CCs should be designed to integrate the wealth of resources already developed by RIs and research organisations in Europe. Although each CC will function as a one-stop-shop for its particular community of users, they will pool expertise from various domains and therefore could also act as a gateway with other clusters.

Core Mission, Focus Areas and Key Actions

The core mission of CCs will be to aid scientific research by increasing the accessibility of research services through awareness, dissemination, training, and support with dedicated resources (including tools and recommendations), to as broad a user community as possible.

This core mission is addressed through two focus areas: i) promoting FAIR data and Open Science, and ii) fostering a support environment for researchers and their teams even if they are not primary users. As outlined below, LS CCs will share these two focus areas and undertake common key actions that will determine exactly how each CC will be configured. CCs are expected to leverage resources and services already existing in the LS-RI landscape to fulfil these missions.

Focus Area 1: Promoting FAIR Data and Open Science

Key Action 1 - Adoption of Open Science and FAIR Data practices: One of the main pillars of Open Science is the adoption of good practices in Data Management (e.g. FAIR principles, data management plans (DMPs) and data dictionaries). A primary action of CCs will be to promote Open Science, building on existing frameworks, tools, and training (Zadissa A, Apweiler R., 2022). These include standards and policies in FAIRsharing (Sansone *et al.*, 2019), resources and guidance for FAIRification (David *et al.*, 2020), the [FAIR Cookbook](#) (Rocca-Serra *et al.*, 2023), certification systems

(e.g. [CoreTrustSeal](#)-like standards, see Canham *et al.*, 2020), registration and mapping of databases at least through metadata (David *et al.* 2023c), and the continued development of community-driven practices to ensure data reliability and trustworthiness. The CCs are expected to support RIs in the integration of flexible FAIRification frameworks into their operations. This will require continual improvement of computational resources and data management solutions. Furthermore, CCs will support the adoption of FAIR and Open Science practices by the research community, for instance, through the integration of workflows into routine RI operations, utilising tools like [WorkflowHub](#), developed through EOSC-Life (Goble *et al.*, 2020, Gustafsson *et al.*, 2024).

Key Action 2 - Building Interoperability and Semantic Harmonisation: CCs can play a central role in advancing interoperability through the development of community-driven standards and ontologies, recommendations, metadata schemas ([over 1400+ in the natural sciences](#)), semantic tools, and real-time data sharing mechanisms. These will enable integration, collaboration, and data reuse across different RIs, facilitating interdisciplinary research (see this example for sensitive data across RIs in the EOSC-Life project (David *et al.*, 2022, Ohmann *et al.*, 2022).

Key Action 3 - Interconnectivity between RIs: CCs should provide researchers with easy access to a broad range of efficient tools and data, guidance for good practices, and technical support, in a way that makes the users' experience similar regardless of the precise focus of the CC. This harmonisation will also include fostering synergies with CCs in other SCs to promote RI cooperation across domains, thereby broadening the reusability of services by making them more composable. Additionally, CCs could rationalise workforce development by tackling skill gaps across the LS-RIs, but also potentially across SCs, by building a more unified approach to human resource development.

Several resources and services that have already been developed within the LS-RI landscape will support these three key actions:

- **Open Science Advocacy & FAIR Tools and Services for Data Management:** LS-RIs, for instance through outputs from 27 projects supported by EOSC-Life ([Achievements - EOSC Life](#)), have played an important role in promoting Open Science practices and fostering transparency, collaboration, and reproducibility in research. Many LS-RIs have built and deployed sophisticated systems for ensuring data is compliant with FAIR principles. These include data curation tools, repositories, and Virtual Research Environments (VREs) that enable researchers to store, analyse, and share their data. VREs serve as crucial components of many RIs, offering cloud-based platforms that integrate data, tools, and computational resources. These environments support a wide range of scientific workflows, from genomic analyses to modelling approaches in Life Sciences, and are central to the ability to offer flexible and scalable services to researchers. Many LS-RIs also provide guidelines, and structured support for researchers, ensuring their data is managed in alignment with FAIR principles, thus improving data reuse and research efficiency (David *et al.*, 2023b).
- **Interoperability and Semantic Harmonisation:** Several of the LS-RIs have led efforts in data management, standardisation and interoperability, contributing to the development of communities of practice, international standards (e.g. [ISO 23494](#) for provenance, [ISO 20387](#) and number of material-specific standards for biobanking, several for the Genomic Standards Consortium ([GSC](#)) and the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health ([GA4GH](#)), through the creation of [Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics \(OHDSI\)](#), its Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model ([OMOP CDM](#)) and [vocabulary](#), involvement in [HL7 Europe](#) with the development of various HL7 FHIR [profiles](#) or grassroots initiatives (such as Minimum Information About Biobank data Sharing ([MIABIS](#)) and Investigation Study Assay JavaScript Object Notation ([ISA JSON](#))). These efforts and several innovative tools for metadata aggregations (e.g. [Rucio](#) (Barisits *et al.*, 2019), [RO-Crate](#) (Peroni *et al.*, 2022), [MAGGOT](#) (Jacob *et al.*, 2025)) help ensure that data across different RIs can be integrated coherently into the FAIR web of data in line with the goals of the EOSC.

- **RI Interconnectivity:** Several LS-RIs offer well-established frameworks for discovering and accessing data and/or data services through federated online platforms that enhance interoperability and integration across multiple infrastructures, facilitating cross-disciplinary research and collaboration across multiple sites and countries (Table 1).

Focus Area 2: Fostering a Support Environment for Researchers

Key Action 1 - Training and Capacity Building: Through training programmes, outreach initiatives and accessible resources, CCs will equip researchers and institutions with the knowledge and skills to implement FAIR principles, and robust data management and Open Science practices. The training programmes will cater to diverse audiences and promote widespread engagement through outreach actions such as hackathons, e-learning events, workshops, and training open calls ([Training - EOSC-Life](#)), but also through the provision of accessible resources (e.g. [FAIRsharing | EOSC-Life](#); Sansone *et al.*, 2019, Zadissa A & Apweiler R., 2022, Hiltmann *et al.*, 2023).

Key Action 2 - Supporting Innovation and Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration: Building on the technical work for RI interconnectivity described above, CCs will act as hubs for accessing tools, repositories, and software, enhancing their discoverability and accessibility for researchers. This will facilitate cross-disciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange. The CCs will also play a key role in supporting large-scale research initiatives, such as building future large scale imaging data ecosystems or enabling rapid data-driven responses to, for example, public health emergencies, such as pandemics, through interoperable data-sharing mechanisms, in collaboration with pertinent international partners, such as the [WHO](#).

Key Action 3 - Fostering Global-Scale Research: Through the institution of common practices and the implementation of shared tools across the LS-RIs, the CCs have the potential to support ambitious federative initiatives. In the healthcare domain, for instance, through increasing data mobilisation and aggregation skills and capacities, CCs might spur collaboration and help accelerate the development of new drugs, vaccines, and diagnostics (Rubinstein *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, the CCs should support RIs in the promotion of harmonised, high-quality, efficient, legally and ethically-compliant data practices. Thereby, the CCs will enhance research replicability, reproducibility and integrity, and allow for efficient exploitation of the opportunities offered through the European Health Data Space (EHDS).

To advance in these actions, the CCs would be expected to build on previous LS-RI services and resources:

- **Training and Capacity Building:** RIs such as ELIXIR (D'Anna *et al.*, 2024), Euro-Biolmaging, and BBMRI offer well-developed training programs on data quality, FAIRification, and best practices for data management and data analysis. These programmes cater to researchers, service providers, and trainers, equipping them with the skills needed to operate in a FAIR Open Science environment ([Training - EOSC-Life](#), [Training-FAIR BioImage Data](#)). They would be expanded, connected and harmonised as much as possible across the CCs. It is worth mentioning that CCs will not replace the functions of the relevant competent national bodies that may currently oversee training and capacity building, but would be expected to promote dialogue and operational alignment between them. In addition, CCs will also seek to promote institutional training programmes tailored to professional skills development for RI data experts, acknowledging and encompassing the diversity of their roles and responsibilities (see for instance the Alan Turing Institute's Skills Policy Research projects (Karoune and Sharan, 2025) and EMBL's [ARISE2 project](#)).
- **Innovation and Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration:** LS-RIs have contributed significantly to building a research community by supporting knowledge-sharing, best practice dissemination, and fostering engagement between researchers, data providers, and infrastructure operators through initiatives such as EOSC-Life. Moreover, LS-RIs are developing an additional category of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and particularly for personal data (General Data Protection Regulation - [GDPR compliance](#)), for which the [EOSC-ENTRUST](#) project is developing a common European Blueprint (Sætrum and Negru,

2024) to enhance and improve capabilities and lower barriers for European researchers. By being involved in the implementation of TREs, the CCs will be able to promote shared standards, essential for cross-disciplinary collaboration.

- Tools for Global-Scale Research:** Several RIs offer collaborative tools that support international and interdisciplinary research, such as shared data repositories, analysis platforms, and terminologies (Matentzoglou *et al.*, 2022), metadata tools (Jacob *et al.*, 2020; Wittner *et al.*, 2022), toolboxes for specific domains like drug discovery and development (Bray *et al.*, 2020, Alharbi *et al.*, 2022), clinical trials ([Adaptive Platform Trial Tools | Ecrin, EJP RD. Innovation Management Toolbox - IMT](#)), and agricultural science (Caracciolo *et al.*, 2020). These tools foster harmonisation of standards and best practices, allowing researchers to work together on complex scientific questions using integrated data and workflows. In addition to supporting research, RIs facilitate training activities through platforms such as the [Bioimage Analysis Desktop \(BAND\)](#), an EOSC-Life output which enables interactive image analysis and collaborative training across multiple institutions.

Challenges for CCs in LS

The focus areas and key actions of the CCs outlined above reflect the growing complexity of interdisciplinary research. The CCs will face several significant challenges that can be grouped into foundational, policy, and technical (Table 2), as detailed below.

Table 2: Main challenges around the implementation of Competence Centres (CCs) in Life Sciences (LS), including targets, stakeholders, and short- as well as long-term solutions, grouped into foundational, policy, and technical categories. The ten challenges and their solutions were identified by the authors of this paper representing the LS-RI community and prioritised using a voting process (Supplementary Material 3).

	CHALLENGE	TARGET	STAKEHOLDER	SHORT-TERM	LONG-TERM
FOUNDATIONAL	Definition and Consensus	Develop a shared vision for CCs through participatory workshops and collaborative publications	LS-RI community, researchers, policymakers	Quick alignment of visions	Uniform implementation of CCs across LS-RIs; Workshops for building community consensus
	Awareness and Community Engagement	Actively disseminate the CC concept through training programmes and outreach initiatives	Researchers, RIs, communication and outreach officers	Immediate increase in CC visibility; Increase participation in CC-led initiatives	Long-term engagement and widespread adoption of CCs
POLICY	Governance Complexity	Streamline governance processes with clear examples and models	CC administration, policymakers, existing infrastructures	Reduction of administrative complexity across governance layers	Efficient and adaptive governance focused on scientific service development
	Incentives for FAIR and Open Science	Encourage the use of community standards and creation of data policies; better link publications to FAIR datasets	Researchers, data stewards, service providers, funding bodies, journal editors	Rapid adoption of FAIR practices, also through rewards and badges	Widespread integration of FAIR practices in the scientific community
	Funding and Policy Alignment	Ensure continuous funding; integrate EOSC guidelines into calls for funding CCs	Funding agencies, (international) policymakers, research institutions	Quick and early compliance with EOSC sustainability models and guidelines	Financial stability and lasting alignment with Open Science policies
	Sustainability and Resource Allocation	Propose robust funding models and KPIs	Infrastructure managers, funders, policymakers, project evaluators	Short-term maintenance of human and financial resources	Long-term viability of CCs as operational entities

	CHALLENGE	TARGET	STAKEHOLDER	SHORT-TERM	LONG-TERM
T E C H N I C A L	Interoperability and Standardisation	Define and adopt harmonised software, tools, and procedures among LS-RIs	Developers, researchers, EOSC expert groups	Adoption of common standards in pilot projects	Full interoperability of FAIR resources at the European level
	Data Stewardship and Quality Control	Promote the role of data stewards and create registries for data management	Data stewards, researchers, RI administrators, data-generating institutions	Immediate improvement in data quality and management	Broader FAIR data exposure and capacity building; integration of FAIR data stewardship into standard research workflows
	Heterogeneous Expertise and Skills Development	Organise funded workshops for upskilling and driving skills development	Researchers, technicians, trainers, RI service and training delivery staff	Better data lifecycle management skills; strengthened cross-RI collaboration on training programmes	Long-term and sustained harmonisation of data management, capacity building, and training practices across CCs
	Technical Infrastructure Architecture	Establish harmonised, federated cloud infrastructures for managing data volumes	Storage / computing solutions and cloud service providers, research institutions, data management professionals	Cost-effective temporary storage solutions for data preparation and analysis; national or domain compute service providers	Robust technical infrastructure aligned with FAIR practices; federated data systems enabling cross-border data access and analysis; EOSC Federation storage / computing solutions and cloud services

Foundational Challenges

Challenge 1 - Definition and Consensus Building: One of the primary challenges in establishing CCs within LS-RIs is the lack of prior consensus. Addressing this requires the development of a shared vision for CCs, achieved through participatory online workshops that engage the LS-RI communities. Tools like Delphi reviews and consensus-building papers can help align diverse stakeholders' views within the community, as demonstrated by this article.

Challenge 2 - Awareness and Community Engagement: Awareness and engagement with CCs among researchers, both within and outside existing RIs, is anticipated to be an issue. Solutions include active dissemination of the CC concept through targeted stakeholder events and community outreach initiatives, such as training programmes. Expanding the number of RIs engaged in each CC would also enhance their visibility and ensure that all LS-RIs can benefit from CC frameworks.

Policy Challenges

Challenge 3 - Governance Complexity: The most appropriate governance, among those pre-defined within EOSC ([Governance Structure | EOSC Governance Framework](#)) will have to be chosen for CCs, to minimise diverting resources from the core mission of CCs, namely advancing scientific services and their accessibility. Simplifying governance processes within CCs and offering clear examples or guidelines for governance mechanisms can help streamline operations. Importantly, the governance model chosen needs to take into account the operational configuration of CCs (see Operational Scenarios of CCs) and be articulated to be compatible with existing RI statutes and practices.

Challenge 4 - Incentives for FAIR and Open Science: Strong incentives are also needed to promote FAIR and Open Science practices among researchers and RIs. Despite EOSC addressing foundational topics, such as persistent identifiers (PIDs), in its "[Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda \(SRIA\)](#)" (Hellström *et al.*, 2020, Schwardmann *et al.*, 2020), the use of long-lasting references, and policies that associate peer-reviewed publications with FAIR/open datasets (and software) are yet to be broadly adopted. In addition, FAIRification of RI services is often incomplete because service delivery staff lack the necessary skills. To exploit the potential of CCs to contribute in

this area would require European funding (see Challenge 5) to increase data management literacy and support better data management practices and Open Science initiatives. This could be complemented by reward systems for contributors and approval badges for repositories adhering to and implementing high-quality standards, for instance through indexation in catalogues, such as [FAIRsharing](#) (Sansone *et al.*, 2019) that cross-links databases to the standards they implement and the policies that recommend them.

Challenge 5 - Policy Alignment and Funding: While the OSCARS project provides financial support to coordinate the design of CCs, there are no dedicated funds to support their widespread adoption across the LS-RI community and beyond. A lack of sustained funding and incentives to implement CCs, or indeed EOSC recommendations and guidelines more generally (Robertson *et al.*, 2024), thus presents another challenge. Any future CC funding should be complementary to, and not competitive with RI funding. The allocation of sufficient resources would allow CCs to operate as well-identifiable entities. Innovation and maintenance in CCs could be in addition supported by thematic Open Calls for projects analogous to those that underpinned actions in [EOSC-Life](#) and [OSCARS](#). As long as there are minimal barriers for adoption, at the policy level, explicit inclusion of FAIR and quality data handling requirements in funding calls can promote widespread implementation. For example, beneficiaries of Horizon Europe funding must commit to managing any digital research data that they generate in line with the FAIR principles.

Challenge 6 - Sustainability and Resource Allocation: Our fundamental premise is that CCs will prove themselves to be a valuable addition to the Open Science landscape and thus merit to be maintained. Long-term sustainability of CCs would, however, present a significant challenge, especially in terms of securing investment in human and capital resources. Proposing robust funding models and establishing key performance indicators (KPIs) to monitor CC activities are critical steps toward maintaining CCs as viable entities. To go forward on technical sustainability, the LS-RIs published 15 recommendations related to sustainable FAIR compliance in data sharing (David *et al.*, 2023b). These recommendations include practical considerations for resource allocation that would be applicable in future CCs, for example, related to the dissemination of best practices for data curation, data mobilisation, data management, or FAIR-related requirements.

Although CCs are yet to be established, it's important that they are designed with long-term sustainability in mind. This is crucial to ensure there is sustained professional recognition of data stewards, and support for efforts and skills to improve the quality of data management, both of which are key to promoting best practices. Without strong data management, data quality is reduced, and there is slower progress on advancing FAIR data practices and training. Effective sustainability and exploitation strategies have to be kept up to date to ensure capacity building efficiency, in alignment with the evolving needs of the community.

Technical Challenges

Challenge 7 - Interoperability and Standardisation: Achieving full interoperability of FAIR data resources among LS-RIs faces challenges in defining and adopting harmonised software, tools, and procedures. Local¹ adaptations of procedures and tools often add complexity, but common standards, registries, and frameworks, as proposed by Barker *et al.* (2022) and Chue Hong *et al.* (2022), can provide a solid foundation to ensure broad interoperability. Sharing of resources, technologies, and lessons learned through online knowledge exchange portals can enhance use of good practices. Finding synergies, and procedures to be shared, between different large-scale, data-driven projects and initiatives are key actions for all stakeholders hoping to improve interoperability within the research landscape; this will particularly apply in the context of future CCs.

Challenge 8 - Data Stewardship and Quality Control: CCs are expected to be supported by data stewards from existing RIs. This should help ensure that there are no gaps in data stewardship that would limit the integration and quality control of data within the LS research ecosystem. Promoting the

¹ When we refer to “local”, here and elsewhere, in addition to geographically-constrained, we also mean thematically or methodologically defined.

role of data stewards particularly in RIs, facilitating knowledge exchange between them through inter-RI events, as well as creating data steward registries and common practices for data stewardship in CCs would help build a stronger data stewardship network across CCs and RIs. This would also help the identification, development, dissemination, and implementation of best practices and tools to facilitate access and reuse of research data and broader capacity building in the LS-RIs network. On a practical level, regarding quality control, the use of PIDs can facilitate version tracking, updating, and use of both databases and tools (Kálmán *et al.*, 2024). Similarly, application of content codes aids audit trailing, and helps maintain quality standards.

Challenge 9 - Heterogeneous Expertise and Skills Development: Disparities in data lifecycle management capacity across CCs will likely present a challenge. Targeted solutions, such as regular workshops, can foster harmonisation, strengthen FAIR implementation, and promote the adoption of the best methods and tools (Papoutsoglou 2020). Leveraging adaptive learning, strategic collaborations, and Continuous Development Programme (CDP) initiatives (e.g. [RItrainPlus](#)) would be expected to upskill CC staff, which is imperative for capacity building in the long term.

Challenge 10 - Technical Infrastructure Architecture: Once the contours and roles of CCs are well established, effective organisation and structuring between technical services will be critical for managing the complexity of data generated from different sources (Soiland-Reyes *et al.*, 2022). This is especially true in decentralised data architectures such as [Gaia-X](#) or the [EHDS](#), or for example for services in the distributed analysis of health data (Hallock *et al.*, 2021), but also for mobilising and aggregating data for necessary meta-analysis to tackle global challenges for LS, for instance related to biodiversity (Pereira *et al.*, 2013), agriculture (Caracciolo *et al.*, 2020), and infectious disease outbreaks (David *et al.*, 2023c; David *et al.*, 2025). Establishing harmonised, federated service infrastructures (like [MyHealth@EU](#), Rujano *et al.*, 2024; the [European Genomic Data Infrastructure, GDI](#)) that can offer cost-effective temporary computational and storage capacities for data preparation and/or analysis will be a crucial technical basis for CCs to operate. This includes the need to support the development, implementation and maintenance of environments for Common Data Elements (CDEs) e.g. [OHDSI/OMOP](#), [MIABIS](#) (Eklund *et al.*, 2024), [BRISQ](#) (Moore *et al.*, 2011) and associated repositories like [NIH CDE Repository](#) to ensure consistent metadata structures harmonisation across domains.

A series of complementary challenges (Supplementary Material 4) was collectively identified, analysed, and prioritised by the authors of this paper through the Radical Collaboration Method. Addressing the main challenges above but also the complementary ones is essential for the successful implementation and operation of LS CCs, and would be necessary to ensure their meaningful contribution to scientific advances and real-world outcomes.

Operational Scenarios for CCs

Among the LS-RIs, there is a consensus that CCs can act as dynamic hubs to foster the uptake of Open Science in Europe, contribute to the EOSC FAIR web of data, and support future development of the EOSC Federation. But, for CCs to be established, there needs to be a clear vision regarding their contours, governance, and operation to optimise support for research.

Taking into consideration the current operational status of LS-RIs, two broad implementation scenarios have emerged: a federated CC network, and an LS-RI community-based centralised CC entity. As detailed in Table 3, both models include measures to overcome the different foundational, policy, and technical hurdles outlined above and in Table 2. Both scenarios necessitate community-driven definition and consensus processes, robust sustainability plans, and adequate technical infrastructure architecture, and need to be supported by sufficient and appropriate data stewardship and skills development.

In a federated CC network, specific roles and responsibilities would be assigned to the different CCs. Federated networks can utilise existing operational frameworks for their federation. On the other hand, a centralised CC entity would operate as a single coordinating authority responsible for

managing resources, roles, and the overall CC network, reducing flexibility but increasing standardisation and central coordination.

Table 3: Main challenges around the implementation of Competence Centres (CCs) in Life Sciences (LS), in federated and centralised operational scenarios. The ten challenges and their solutions were identified by the authors of this paper representing the LS-RI community and prioritised using a voting process (Supplementary Material 3).

	CHALLENGES	REQUIRED ACTION	CENTRALISED SCENARIO	
FOUNDATIONAL	Definition and Consensus	Launch participatory workshops across LS-RIs to define the CC's scope and mission.	In both operational scenarios, this step will need to be community-driven to maximise convergence on common concepts and definition(s). Effort: Stakeholders must stay involved in this process to ensure long-term engagement and wide consensus between communities.	
	Awareness and Community Engagement	Foster engagement through targeted outreach, emphasising the benefits of each approach.	Tailored, region- and context-specific outreach strategies. Effort: align and harmonise messaging across stakeholders.	One coherent and coordinated outreach strategy, ensuring consistent messaging. Effort: ensure stakeholder engagement.
POLICY	Governance Complexity	Implement the pre-defined EOSC governance model with clear roles and responsibilities, while avoiding administrative redundancies.	Requires a distributed governance structure with well-defined roles and responsibilities. Effort: Cross-CC coordination for structural consistency.	A single representative governance body (e.g. a CC board) simplifies decision-making and ensures clear accountability. Effort: Minimise bureaucratic inefficiencies.
	Incentives for FAIR and Open Science	Encourage FAIR data practices through reward systems and recognition within each CC.	Incentives will depend on the level of awareness, readiness, and literacy regarding FAIR and Open Science across the distributed network. Effort: Strategy must ensure the policy landscape is inclusive and flexible and include efficient incentives to allow new and developing communities to align with FAIR and Open Science requirements.	Application of incentives can be generalised for all CCs. It will be easier to allocate them fairly based on clear and targeted criteria. Effort: Reduce barriers to access of incentives for FAIR and Open Science. Drive the increase of FAIR and Open Science literacy centrally, while considering specific communities' needs.
	Policy Alignment and Funding	Secure funding for individual CCs while aligning them with overarching EOSC policies.	CCs can apply relevant regulations in different contexts and environments. This influences funding availability of CC services. Effort: Harmonise RIs policies (e.g. through EOSC) across federated networks.	Policy alignment requires flexible and established funding models (e.g., cascade funds) to distribute resources equitably across CCs. Effort: Funding must reinforce literacy and awareness for less advanced communities.
	Sustainability and Resource Allocation	Secure continuous funding through EC grants and integrate EOSC recommendations.	Both scenarios need strong and well-structured sustainability plans with well-allocated resources. Effort: Sustainability plans must cater to different CC needs and uses. While centrally managed sustainability facilitates resource allocation, some communities may struggle to access dedicated funding for domain-specific initiatives, curbing their potential.	
TECHNICAL	Interoperability and Standardisation	Implement harmonised tools and software standards to ensure seamless data integration.	A federated framework relies on the implementation of common standards across the CC network. Effort: Allow for local adaptations, to ensure interoperability while promoting innovation.	Top-down standardisation efforts ensure uniform interoperability. Effort: Flexibility is required through ongoing reviews to allow for innovation in specific contexts.
	Data Stewardship and Quality Control	Create a central registry for data stewards, promoting consistent data quality practices.	Both scenarios require good data stewardship and quality control. Effort: Data stewards have to adapt the way they operate to take into account the governance model, policy landscape, resources and awareness.	

CHALLENGES	REQUIRED ACTION	CENTRALISED SCENARIO	
Heterogeneous Expertise and Skills Development	Organise cross-RI workshops to harmonise skills and knowledge sharing.	Both scenarios require ongoing knowledge exchange and education. Effort: Training teams have to adapt their strategy in identifying training needs based on awareness and literacy, but also designing and executing training depending on these needs, available funding, and resources.	
Technical Infrastructure Architecture	Establish federated cloud infrastructures that allow for local autonomy while ensuring interoperability.	In both cases, a solid architectural foundation is required to allow for storage and computing services and data exchange between CCs. Effort: Technical infrastructure managers must ensure their tools and interfaces are continuously rationalised and adapted to the needs of specific communities.	

The primary advantage of a **federated CC network** would be its flexibility. LS-RIs would retain full ownership and responsibility over their specific data, methods, and knowledge, ensuring that local oversight is preserved even within a broader, cooperative framework. This would allow LS-RIs to tailor CCs to their specific needs while fostering collaboration without diluting the availability of specialised expertise and the support structures essential for domain-specific data services. A federated CC network is inherently scalable, making it adaptable to various disciplines and regional contexts. Ensuring consistent quality and interoperability across diverse CCs would, however, be a challenge, requiring strong coordination mechanisms. Additionally, the distributed governance of a federated system of CCs would be more complex, necessitating well-defined roles and processes to maintain efficiency.

On the other hand, a **central CC entity** would promote uniform standards and practices across LS-RIs, ensuring the enhancement of data management quality, but also consistent and efficient LS-RI service delivery through CCs. It would also facilitate centralised training and resource allocation, optimising cost efficiency and reducing duplication of efforts. Moreover, policy alignment and governance are streamlined by a centralised decision-making system, simplifying compliance with overarching frameworks such as the one provided by the EOSC. Nevertheless, this model would require careful coordination and adequate resourcing to function effectively. Resistance from LS-RIs that prioritise autonomy may also arise, and the initial investment for establishing a centralised entity could be significant.

Discussion

While above we have described two distinct organisational models - fully centralised and federated respectively - in practice, the most effective approach will likely combine elements from both. A mixed operational model, specifically, a network of CC spokes federated through a jointly-coordinated central hub (**hub-and-spoke model**), combines the strengths of both centralised and federated approaches, effectively addressing the actions outlined in Table 3 and the related implementation steps.

This hybrid model allows for a coherent overarching strategy, and unified governance, through **central hub(s)**, enhancing accountability, simplifying policy alignment and funding, for instance, through cascading grants. Central hubs can standardise messaging, interoperability guidelines, and incentives for FAIR and Open Science, creating more consistency and equity across the network.

At the same time, the **federated spokes** enable local flexibility, ensuring that outreach and engagement strategies resonate with the targeted user communities, and can be adapted to regional, thematic, or methodological contexts, fostering effective and efficient exchange among and between scientific communities, and therefore innovation. At the same time, each federated spoke retains clearly defined roles and responsibilities within the network, maintaining operational agility and minimising bureaucratic governance. Importantly, defining the concrete roles and responsibilities, in alignment with the focus areas and key actions, will constitute a key step in the implementation of CCs.

This hybrid model would ensure effective and flexible resource allocation, leveraging centralised efficiency for broad strategic goals, while still accommodating specific domain-driven initiatives within local communities and their environments. The central hub would serve as a coordination point and distributors of key resources, while federated spokes ensure direct applicability, community buy-in, and adaptability.

Therefore, the **hub-and-spoke model** emerges as a **balanced operational framework**, offering both strategic coherence and the flexibility necessary for successful CC implementation across LS-RIs, and perhaps even SCs. It could facilitate the management of shared missions, skills, and resources that are common across all LS-RIs, offering harmonisation and unified frameworks (Figure 2). This unified framework is a prerequisite for promoting FAIR data and Open Science, and for the core mission of CCs to provide accessible research services and environments to a broad user community.

Competence Centre (CC) Model for LS-RIs

Figure 2: The selection of a model for the organisation of LS-RI Competence Centres (CCs) hinges on balancing inclusivity, interoperability, and sustainability. A central CC entity (right hand circle) ensures broad standardisation, reduces administrative burdens, and helps secure long-term funding, while enhancing data management consistency. A federated CC network (left hand circle) fosters cross-RI collaboration, maximises flexibility, and strengthens FAIR adoption while maintaining autonomy. The hybrid hub-and-spoke model (central oval), a network of CCs federated through central hubs - which exists within each SC and jointly align on and coordinate CC activities - combines joint coordination with distributed expertise, optimising governance, harmonisation, and stakeholder satisfaction.

Figure 3 illustrates a phased approach to implement this hybrid **hub-and-spoke CC model** that combines central SC hubs with federated CC spokes. By integrating foundational, policy, and technical layers, the model balances collaborative alignment and coordination of activities with local flexibility.

At the **foundational level**, participatory processes and community engagement would help define the CCs' scope. Key cornerstones would be to maximise convergence on common concepts and definitions and to encourage community engagement through more and better awareness. Launching stakeholder workshops and tailoring outreach strategies at the local level would ensure both inclusiveness and relevance, and help sustain stakeholder engagement in the long term. The hybrid model would combine central coordination with local community-specific input, and optimise engagement through coherent yet context-sensitive communication.

In the **policy layer**, coherence would be achieved by linking CC actions to a shared strategic framework. The hybrid model would support:

- i) central overarching governance supported by clearly defined roles at CC spokes,
- ii) central funding distribution catering to the needs of the CC spokes,
- iii) centralised but context-aware incentive schemes for FAIR and Open Science, and
- iv) flexible, long-term and needs-driven resource allocation.

Central hubs would streamline governance, align policy, and coordinate funding, while spokes would retain flexibility and local adaptability in needs-driven resource allocation and transparent distribution of incentives tailored to community-specific needs through a well established governance framework.

In the **technical layer**, the central coordinating hub would provide service support and standards, while the federated spokes would adapt tools to local or domain-specific needs, ensuring both interoperability and flexibility without hindering local innovation. Moreover, the hub would ensure data stewardship frameworks are harmonised but managed locally to meet community-specific contexts. Central hubs would coordinate knowledge-sharing programmes, while federated spokes would adapt training to local skills needs. An overall robust and interoperable technical infrastructure with

region-specific adaptability would ensure consistent quality and local ownership.

In practice, the hub-and-spoke model would allow LS-RIs to coordinate the CC network jointly through a central environment (for example, [LifeScience RI](#)), while CCs would exist locally as defined spokes.

Figure 3: Framework for implementing a European Network of Competence Centres in Life Sciences using a hub-and-spoke model. The structure spans three layers. Foundational Layer: Establishes the mission, scope, and collaborative alignment of CCs across national and international stakeholders. Policy Layer: Defines governance roles, fosters FAIR and Open Science through incentives, and ensures policy alignment and sustainable resource allocation. Technical Layer: Supports interoperability, data stewardship, skills development, and the integration of distributed technical infrastructure architectures.

Fostering Collaboration and Simplification

Despite the challenges, CCs will provide a valuable opportunity to foster collaboration and bring more coherency in the research landscape. By clearly defining their roles and adopting standardised governance models aligned with the EOSC framework, CCs can act as key enablers of interdisciplinary collaboration. This includes building partnerships with other SCs to promote cross-domain innovation and to facilitate data sharing.

Defining the interactions between all CC stakeholders will be crucial, and for this clear roles and responsibilities would need to be assigned. For instance, CCs could prioritise the delivery of domain-specific expertise and training. Such a structured delineation of responsibilities would help ensure that CCs complement, rather than replicate, existing capabilities which already exist within LS-RIs.

Low awareness among researchers, both within and outside RIs, would limit use of services, expertise, and related support provided by CCs. To remedy this, the potential user communities of CCs would need to be precisely identified. This would allow their common practices to be mapped, a prerequisite for the delivery of tailored support and training, as well as for outreach and communication efforts adapted to the level of knowledge and awareness of potential end users. Other than communicating the benefits of CCs, **creating incentives and ensuring that each CC complements LS-RIs in addressing domain-specific challenges** could foster greater involvement. This could be complemented by reward systems for contributors and approval badges for repositories

adhering to and implementing high-quality standards, for instance through indexation in catalogues such as FAIRsharing (Sansone *et al.*, 2019) that cross-links databases to the standards they implement and the policies that recommend them.

In the short term, as these awareness campaigns, training, and recognition systems increase the visibility of CC benefits, user engagement will improve. In the long term, an expanded and engaged user base will strengthen CC sustainability and promote broader adoption of FAIR and Open Science practices. The use of recognition systems, through persistent digital identifiers (e.g., DOIs, ORCIDs, ROR) for data, software, publications, and citations, can also provide a lasting incentive for some researchers. Additionally, incorporating equity in sustainability plans is central to the long-term success of CCs to ensure broad stakeholder satisfaction and engagement. As current funding schemes often lack continuity, if CCs demonstrate their utility, it will be critical to **develop a sustainable funding framework, potentially including complementary EC funding lines and public-private partnerships**. In the long term, financial sustainability will ensure that CC resources remain continuously available, embedding CC functions within the scientific community to support open data sharing.

Efficient collaboration is i) highly supported by interoperability and ii) fundamental for successful CC operations. This might be hindered by complex governance structures which could detract from scientific service development. **Streamlined governance, along with established frameworks for interoperability** (e.g. standard APIs, common and well recognized and indexed metadata standards), would ensure more efficient collaboration. Single access point cross-domain registries like the FAIRsharing platform which was co-created with support through EOSC-Life provide an example for such community driven solutions. EOSC Task Forces and workshops can further contribute to developing harmonised standards, enabling CCs to offer cohesive, cross-disciplinary services. **Simplified governance increases agility necessary for CCs to provide researchers with adequate expert support** without unnecessary administrative complexity. In the short term, simplified governance improves decision-making and enables CCs to prioritise scientific service development. Long-term efficiencies include a more cohesive data ecosystem that supports seamless cross-disciplinary research, enhancing CC impact and usability.

If in the future CCs are to exploit the potential for cross-SC collaboration, there will need to be a reinforcement of synergy-building mechanisms. **Regularly funded workshops across SCs, but also across nationally and internationally funded projects, would foster more efficient collaboration**, allowing CCs to leverage diverse expertise and resources. Enhanced coordination, particularly in aligning software, tools, and procedures, is crucial to enabling meaningful integration. Long-term efficiencies include established synergies that make CCs more responsive to interdisciplinary research needs, strengthening the LS-RI ecosystem.

The advent of new technologies such as AI and the increasing interest in the analysis of multi-modal datasets drives interdisciplinary science. Combining and analysing heterogeneous data is a prerequisite for solving societal challenges such as infectious disease outbreaks, environmental disasters and loss of biodiversity. This will only be possible if there is successful integration of diverse data across RIs with differing standards and protocols, which in turn requires both technical solutions and dedicated resources. Therefore, **interoperability of data and other research objects remains one of the greatest challenges and one that CCs could materially contribute to solving**.

The main way to help researchers access and analyse data across domains effectively is to promote a FAIR web of data by **establishing common standards, creating flexible APIs, and providing adaptable cloud-based platforms**. These good practices and tools help increase FAIRness and constitute important objectives for CCs, mainly because linked data are key components for fostering interoperability. For example, linking imaging and structural protein data, enabled by interoperability between the two, has supported the emergence of single-particle cryo-electron microscopy, and more generally opens the path for new technologies and innovation (Kemmer *et al.*, 2023). CCs will help increase interoperability, but the solutions must be designed with a high level of input from their potential end users, i.e. researchers, who are increasingly aware of the potential of interdisciplinary

approaches. In the short term, data-sharing and research accessibility can be enhanced through improved interoperability. In the long term, well-established interoperability will position CCs as key data entities, amplifying their impact across domains and enabling effective cross-discipline research.

The increase of open and reproducible research practices is a driver of global data sharing. Acceptable and effective reuse of data requires high-quality FAIR-compliant data that respects ethical and legal guidelines. To support this, CCs need to develop **clear frameworks and standards, alongside compliance tools, to steward data quality and quality of data management**. Inclusive quality assessment processes, supported by community-driven self-service resources, such as checklists, toolkits ([Infectious Diseases Toolkit](#)) and toolboxes ([Multi-omics Toolbox - MOTBX](#)), guidelines ([FAIR Cookbook](#)) and playbooks ([IHI Data Sharing Playbook](#)), can help establish best practices. Additionally, scalable technical infrastructure architecture will need to be implemented to accommodate the large and increasingly complex computational needs, and storage demands, of the research community, while maintaining compliance with FAIR and good quality data practices. In the short term, like any modern robust technical data infrastructure, CCs must be based on tools and practices that improve data quality, particularly data consistency, through adherence to established standards and the use of compliance tools. In the long-term, strengthening the credibility and reliability of CCs will be a prerequisite for increasing community-wide recognition and use of CC capacities.

Conclusion

If the 10 main challenges as described in this paper are addressed, CCs may represent a transformative opportunity for LS-RIs to promote FAIR and Open Science and foster a support environment for researchers. They can serve as platforms for increasing the exchange of good practices, and interdisciplinary collaborations and synergies across domains. Clear definitions, structured EOSC integration, streamlined governance, interdisciplinary collaboration, and strong incentives for robust interoperability, for data quality frameworks, and for Open Science are key priorities.

By implementing coordinated strategies and targeted solutions, CCs can become sustainable entities within EOSC, fostering collaboration and strengthening Europe's leadership in Open Science and innovation. These strategies include:

- **Unified Vision:** To maximise their potential, CCs require clear definitions, roles, and responsibilities that align with the wider stakeholder community but also the broader goals of EOSC.
- **Engagement:** The success of CCs hinges on active engagement with the scientific community. By implementing funding models with public-private support, alongside career recognition systems, CCs can foster a culture of FAIR and Open Science, ensuring longevity.
- **Streamlined Governance and Interoperability:** Simplified governance frameworks based on cross-cluster interoperability is fundamental to effective and efficient CC operation. Harmonised standards for data and software will enable seamless access and integration across scientific domains, promoting interdisciplinary research.
- **Incentives for Quality and Compliance:** Data quality, FAIR compliance, and adherence to ethical guidelines must be core tenets of CC operations. By establishing robust quality assessment principles and incentives for FAIR practices, CCs can ensure that their resources are reliable, accessible, and responsibly managed.

While European LS-RIs will continue to provide access to cutting-edge technologies, data, and expertise regardless of the implementation of CCs, the CCs would undoubtedly facilitate the secondary use of data and enable connectivity between existing data resources, providing critical mass for the use of AI, thus making science more effective and efficient. By leveraging CCs, LS-RIs would improve findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of resources, strengthening support for European researchers—especially in the health and food domain—while fostering innovation and addressing collaboratively global challenges.

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AAIs	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure services
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AISBL	Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif
API	Application Programming Interfaces
BBMRI	Biobanking and BioMolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
BRISQ	Biospecimen Reporting for Improved Study Quality
CARE4	Collective Benefits, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics
CC	Competence Centre
CCC	Cluster Competence Centre
CCSDS	Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems
CDE(s)	Common Data Element(s)
CDP	Continuous Development Plan
CLOCC	CLuster Open Science Competence Centre
CODAS	Composable Open Data and Analysis Services
CORBEL	Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-Science Services
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EATRIS	European Infrastructure for Translational Medicine
EC	European Commission
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
EDIC	European Digital Infrastructure Consortia
EHDS	European Health Data Space
ELIXIR	European Life Sciences Infrastructure for Life Science Information
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBL-EBI	EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute
EMPHASIS	European Infrastructure for Multi-Scale Plant Phenotyping and Simulation
EMMA	European Mouse Mutant Archive
EMO BON	European Marine Omics Biodiversity Observatory Network
ENVRI	Environmental Research Infrastructures
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-Life	European Open Science Cloud for Life Sciences
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ERINHA	European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESCAPE	European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle Physics ESFRI Research Infrastructures
EU-OPENSOURCE	European Infrastructure of Open Screening Platforms for Chemical Biology
EURO-BIOIMAGING	European Research Infrastructure for Imaging Technologies in Biological and Biomedical Sciences
EVA	European Virus Archive
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FMI	Flanders Marine Institute
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics & Health
GDI	Genomic Data Infrastructure

GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IMT	Innovation Management Toolbox
INSERM	Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale
INSTRUCT	Integrated Structural Biology Infrastructure
INFRAFRONTIER	European Research Infrastructure for the generation, phenotyping, archiving and distribution of in vivo/in vitro model systems and related data
LS	Life Sciences
LS-RI	Life Science Research Infrastructure
MIABIS	Minimum Information About Biobank Data Sharing
MIAPPE	Minimum Information About a Plant Phenotyping Experiment
MIRRI	Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
OSCARS	Open Science Clusters for Advanced Research Solutions
PIDs	Persistent Identifiers
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RI(s)	Research Infrastructure(s)
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
ROR	Research Organisation Registry
SC	Science Cluster
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
SSSOM	Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings
TF	Task Force
TRE	Trusted Research Environment
VREs	Virtual Research Environments
WHO	World Health Organisation

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- **ANAEE: Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems**
ANAEE
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 - **ANAEE Services**
ANAEE
Available at: <https://www.anaee.eu/services> (Accessed: February 2025).
 - **ANAEE Data and Models Portals**
ANAEE
Available at: <https://www.anaee.eu/services/data-and-models-portals> (Accessed: February 2025).
- **ARISE2: Career Accelerator for Research Infrastructure Scientists 2nd generation**
 - Programme website: https://www.embl.org/training/arise2/#vf-tabs__section-programme
 - CORDIS: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101178241>
- **BBMRI-ERIC: Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure**
BBMRI-ERIC
Available at: <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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- **Competence Centres for Social Innovation | European Social Fund Plus**
European Commission
Available at: <https://european-social-fund-plus.ec.europa.eu/en/competence-centres-social-innovation> (Accessed: February 2025).
- **Competency Centres | University of Oxford**
University of Oxford
Available at: <https://staff.admin.ox.ac.uk/competency-centres> (Accessed: February 2025).
- **CORBEL: Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-Science Services**
CORBEL Project
Available at: <https://www.corbel-project.eu/home.html> (Accessed: February 2025).
- **DANUBIUS-RI: The International Centre for Advanced Studies on River-Sea Systems**
DANUBIUS-RI
Available at: <https://danubius-pp.eu/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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University of Geneva
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EATRIS-ERIC
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ECRIN-ERIC
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 - **ECRIN Training**
ECRIN-ERIC
Available at: <https://ecrin.org/training> (Accessed: February 2025).
- **ELIXIR: A Distributed Infrastructure for Life-Science Information**
ELIXIR
Available at: <https://elixir-europe.org/> (Accessed: February 2025).
 - **ELIXIR Services**
ELIXIR
Available at: <https://elixir-europe.org/services> (Accessed: February 2025).
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ELIXIR
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 - **EMBL Services & Facilities**
EMBL
Available at: <https://www.embl.org/services-facilities/> (Accessed: February 2025).
 - **EMBL-EBI (European Bioinformatics Institute)**
EMBL-EBI
Available at: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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EMBL
Available at: <https://www.embl.org/services-facilities/hamburg/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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EMBL
Available at: <https://www.embl.org/services-facilities/grenoble/synchrotron-beamline-access/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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EMBL
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EMBL
Available at: <https://www.embl.org/training/> (Accessed: February 2025).
- **EMBRC-ERIC: European Marine Biological Resource Centre**
EMBRC-ERIC
Available at: <https://www.embrc.eu/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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EMBRC-ERIC
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EMBRC-ERIC
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EMBRC-ERIC
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 - **Marine Training Platform**
Marine Training
Available at: <https://www.marinetraining.eu/home> (Accessed: February 2025).
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EMPHASIS Project
Available at: <https://emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu/>
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Available at: <https://emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu/services/emphasis-pilots/data-services>
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EMPHASIS Project
Available at: <https://emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu/services/emphasis-pilots/training-pilot>
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ENVRI Community
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EOSC Association
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Zenodo
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EOSC Association
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- **ESCAPE: The European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle Physics ESFRI Research Infrastructures**
ESCAPE Project
Available at: <https://projectescape.eu/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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Euro-Biolmaging ERIC
Available at: <https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/training/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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EVA
Available at: <https://www.european-virus-archive.com/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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EVERSE Project: : Research Software & Open Science
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INFRAFRONTIER
Available at: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/> (Accessed: February 2025).
 - **INFRAFRONTIER Services**
INFRAFRONTIER
Available at: <https://infrafrontier.eu/services/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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INFRAFRONTIER
Available at: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/emma/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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INFRAFRONTIER
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Instruct-ERIC
Available at: <https://instruct-eric.eu/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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LS-RI Community Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure services (AAIs).
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LifeWatch ERIC
Available at: <https://www.lifewatch.eu/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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LifeWatch
Available at: <https://trainingcatalogue.lifewatch.eu/home/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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MIRRI-ERIC
Available at: <https://www.mirri.org/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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MIRRI-ERIC
Available at: <https://www.mirri.org/services/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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MIRRI-ERIC
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OSCARS Initiative
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- **OStrails: Open Science Trails for Research Software and Data**
OStrails Project
Available at: <https://ostrails.eu/> (Accessed: February 2025).
 - **OStrails Thematic Pilots (Formatted Web Resource)**
OStrails Project
Available at: <https://ostrails.eu/thematic-pilots> (Accessed: February 2025).
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PaNOSC Project
Available at: <https://www.panosc.eu/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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RltrainPlus Project
Available at: <https://rltrainplus.eu/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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Science Clusters Initiative
Available at: <https://science-clusters.eu/> (Accessed: February 2025).
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Society RSE
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Acknowledgements

This work is mainly a product of LS-RIs representatives. Complementary support was provided through the Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society (OSCARS) European project under grant agreement N°[101129751](#), with a special thanks for the help and advice of the communication team. The authors would like to express their gratitude to the various European research initiatives and projects that have significantly contributed to this work through funding, infrastructure, and collaborative support. In particular, we acknowledge the support of the following projects that received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme:

AI4Life (Grant No. 101057970)	EOSC4Cancer (Grant No. 101058427)
ARISE2 (Grant No. 101178241)	ERIC FORUM (Grant No. 101124559)
BY-COVID (Grant No. 101046203)	EVORA (Grant No. 101131959)
DANUBIUS-IP (Grant No. 101079778)	EVERSE (Grant No. 101129744)
EATRIS-CONNECT (Grant No. 101130349)	FoundingGIDE (Grant No. 101130216)
ENVRI Hub next (Grant No. 101131141)	IMAGINE (Grant No. 101094250)
EOSC Beyond (Grant No. 101131875)	ISIDORe (Grant No. 101046133)
EOSC-ENTRUST (Grant No. 101131056)	Microbes4Climate (Grant No. 101131818)
EOSC-Life (Grant No. 824087)	OSTrails (Grant No. 101130187)

We also recognize the invaluable contributions of these initiatives in fostering collaboration and advancing research in data management, interoperability, and scientific innovation. Finally, we extend our appreciation to all partners, researchers, and technical teams involved in these initiatives for their efforts in promoting Open Science and Competence Centers for data-driven research excellence.

We are grateful to the following LS-RIs and their representatives who endorsed this manuscript: Michel Boër - AnaEE; Petr Holub - BBMRI; Gary Saunders - EATRIS; Shachar Dvir - EIRENE; Tim Hubbard, Andrew Smith, Jonathan Tedds - ELIXIR; Stijn Dhondt - EMPHASIS; Jana Klanova, Audrey Richard & Diana Stepanyan - ERINHA; Linda Chaabane, John Eriksson, Antje Keppler - Euro-Biolmaging; Bruno Coutard - EVA; Vitor Martins dos Santos, Michael O'Donohue - IBISBA; Michael Raess - INFRAFRONTIER; Claudia Alen Amaro, Natalie Haley, Harald Schwalbe - Instruct-ERIC; Ana Portugal Melo - MIRRI-ERIC; Phil Gribbon - EU-OPENSREEN.

We especially thank Claire Connellan for all constructive logistical help and comments.

Competing Interests & disclaimer

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

“OSCARS and other projects supporting this paper are funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union, nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

CrediT authorship contribution statement

- Conceptualisation: RD, AR, NL, APM
- Method: RD
- Original Draft Preparation: RD, NL
- Writing Paper: All authors
- Reviewing & editing paper: All authors
- Visualisation: AR, NL, RD

- Supervision: GS, JE

How AI is used to help writing this paper (commercial version):

- Rewording and style.
- Tracking and removing redundancies.
- Ordering arguments.
- Checking forms considering the journal requirements and the final review (such as reference formats, link availability).
- Summarising structured input from different RIs.

Data Availability statement

CC-By licence - Data contact: Romain David romain.david@erinha.eu +0033 769104341; all data and supplementary material is also available on the OSCARS project's Zenodo web page: [Life Science Competence Centres: Open by Design](#).

Supplementary Material

Supplementary Material 1: Research services and resources provided by ESFRI LS-RIs which participated in a mapping survey through the OSCARS project, categorised into data & databases, technologies and facilities, computational tools, expertise & support, and materials. This version includes all stakeholders who participated in this exercise.

ESFRI LS-RIs *EOSC-Life partner	DOMAIN / COMPETENCE	SERVICES & RESOURCES TO DATE Data & Databases, Technologies & Facilities, Computational Tools, Expertise & Support, Materials	URL
BBMRI-ERIC *	BIOBANKING & BIOMOLECULAR RESOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biobank samples and data services • Interoperability, traceability support • Quality management & ELSI services • Biobanking service support • Training 	https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/bbmri-sample-and-data-portal/ https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/howtomiabis/ https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/services/quality-management/ https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/services-support/ https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/services/e-learning/
EATRIS-ERIC *	TRANSLATIONAL MEDICINE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translational medicine technologies and facilities • Expert centres • Innovation management expertise • Self-service translational medicine resources • Training (TRANSMED Academy) 	https://eatris.eu/infrastructure/product-platforms/ https://eatris.eu/eatris-expert-centres/ https://eatris.eu/innovation-services/ https://eatris.eu/self-service-resources/ https://eatris.eu/transmed-academy/
ECRIN *	CLINICAL TRIALS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical trials services • Clinical trials tools • Training 	https://ecrin.org/clinical-trials https://ecrin.org/tools https://ecrin.org/training
ELIXIR *	CURATED DATABASES & BIOINFORMATICS SERVICES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deposition databases • Data curation services, guidelines • Interoperability services and support • Training & training database 	https://elixir-europe.org/services https://elixir-europe.org/platforms Catalogues include resources hosted across the ELIXIR Nodes (including EMBL-EBI)
EMBRC-ERIC *	MARINE BIOLOGY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine biology technologies & services • Data analysis services • Marine biological resources • Training 	https://www.embrc.eu/services https://trace-embrc.eu/ https://www.marinetraining.eu/home
EMPHASIS *	PLANT PHENOTYPING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plant phenotyping services • Data services • Training 	https://emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu/services https://emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu/services/emphasis-pilots
ERINHA *	HIGHLY PATHOGENIC MICROORGANISMS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to high containment facilities • Biosafety and Biosecurity Expertise • Training 	https://erinha.eu/access-our-services/scientific-services/ https://erinha.eu/erinha-scientific-strategy/unique-facilities-and-scientists/ https://erinha.eu/access-our-services/training/
EU-OPENSREEN ERIC *	CHEMICAL BIOLOGY & DRUG DISCOVERY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chem. Bio. & Med. Chem. services • Chem. Bio. compound collections • Chemical biology database (ECBD) • Training 	https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/services https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/services/training
EURO-BIOIMAGING ERIC *	BIOLOGICAL & BIOMEDICAL IMAGING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Imaging technologies & services • Image analysis services (bioimage desktop) • FAIR data services & support • Training 	https://www.eurobioimaging-access.eu/service https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/data-services/ https://band.vm.fedcloud.eu/#/eosc-landingpage https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/training/
IBISBA	BIOMANUFACTURING SERVICES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biomanufacturing services • FAIR data services & support • Training 	https://ibisba.eu/one-stop-shop/ https://hub.ibisba.eu/
INFRAFRONTIER ERIC *	DISEASE MODELS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disease models services • Mutant models repository and FAIR data resource (EMMA) • Training 	https://infrafrontier.eu/services/ https://www.infrafrontier.eu/emma/ https://infrafrontier.eu/training-events/
INSTRUCT-ERIC *	STRUCTURAL BIOLOGY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structural biology & analysis services • Training 	https://instruct-eric.org/platform-catalogue https://instruct-eric.org/training
MIRRI-ERIC *	MICROBIAL RESOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbial research services • Microbial resources (and data) • Training 	https://www.mirri.org/services/ https://www.mirri.org/microbial-resources-data/ https://www.mirri.org/training-education/
ANAEE-ERIC	ECOSYSTEMS ANALYSIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecosystem research & analysis services • Data and models portals 	https://www.anaee.eu/services https://www.anaee.eu/services/data-and-models-portals
DANUBIUS - RI	RIVER-SEA SYSTEMS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • River-sea systems research services 	https://danubius-ri.eu/

LIFEWATCH ERIC	BIODIVERSITY & ECOSYSTEMS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity and ecosystem data services • Training 	https://www.lifewatch.eu/ https://trainingcatalogue.lifewatch.eu/home/
EMBL**	LIFE SCIENCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data curation services • Data, tools, compute and interoperability platforms • Experimental facilities & analytical platforms • Imaging & analysis services • Training & competency hub 	https://www.embl.org/services-facilities/ https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ https://www.embl.org/services-facilities/hamburg/ https://www.embl.org/services-facilities/grenoble/synchrotron-beamline-access/ https://www.embl.org/about/info/imaging-centre/ https://www.embl.org/training/ https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/
EVA**	VIROLOGICAL RESOURCES & SERVICES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Viral collection (and data) • Virus-derived products (and data) • Services and training in virology • High-throughput sequencing (data generation) 	https://www.european-virus-archive.com/evag-portal-list/field_product_type/virus-55 https://www.european-virus-archive.com/evag-portal-list/field_product_type/derived-product-10150 https://www.european-virus-archive.com/evag-portal-list/field_product_type/derived-product-10150/field_product_type/service-5622 https://www.european-virus-archive.com/evag-portal-list/field_product_type/derived-product-10150/field_product_type/service-5622?portal_search=training High throughput sequencing
CROSS-DOMAIN PLATFORMS & REGISTRIES		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> FAIRsharing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> LS-RI website <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EOSC platform	https://fairsharing.org/ https://lifescience-ri.eu/html https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/

Supplementary Material 2: This glossary provides definitions of key terms and concepts relevant to the development and implementation of Competence Centres (CCs) in the Life Science (LS) domain. It aims to support a shared understanding across stakeholders and ensure clarity in the interpretation of terms used throughout the paper.

Term	Definition
Competence Centre (CC) (OSCARS project)	The term Competence Centre is used in different contexts to describe an infrastructure dedicated to knowledge organisation and transfer, and may have different meanings according to focus area, scope, domain, and socio-economic framework ² . It is usually associated with excellence, training and knowledge transfer, interdisciplinarity, standardisation, and a collaborative approach of different institutions or departments.
Competence Centre (CC) (from the authors)	Competence Centres serve as a single point of reference in their respective countries, regions or thematic domains for i) sensibilisation, ii) dissemination and iii) explanation and advice finding training programmes and materials, best practices and tools for supporting the implementation, management, reuse, sharing and analysis of digital research objects.
Cluster Open Science Competence Centre (CLOCC)	More recently, the OSCARS project team proposed a generic definition of Clusters' Competence Centers: "A CLuster Open Science Competence Centre ³ (CLOCC) is a virtual hub dedicated to fostering research excellence through training and knowledge transfer. The CLOCCs are community-based initiatives supported by a collaborative network of people in the context of the Science Clusters providing expertise, best practices and services in relation to Open Science, and the promotion of cross-disciplinary collaboration."
Composable Open Data and Analysis Services (CODAS)	Composable Open Data and Analysis Services, emphasizing modular and reusable research data services. OSCARS develops CODAS to support diverse research needs across disciplines.
Research Infrastructure (RI) ⁴	RI are facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. They include: major scientific equipment (or sets of instruments), knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives and scientific data, e infrastructures, such as data and computing systems and communication networks and any other tools that are essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation."
Life Science RIs (LS-RIs) ⁵	European Life Science Research Infrastructures (LS-RI) serve excellent science in Europe by providing needed access to world-class facilities, samples, instruments, services, and data. The European LS-RIs were established to overcome a technology gap and to allow access to much-needed technologies in modern research approaches. They have the mission to support cutting-edge science by offering access to the latest technologies, comprehensive resource collections and technical expertise.
European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) ⁶	The European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) is a specific legal form that facilitates the establishment and operation of Research Infrastructures with European interest. The ERIC allows the establishment and operation of new or existing Research Infrastructures on a non-economic basis.
European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ⁷	The ambition of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is to provide European researchers, innovators, companies and citizens with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes. This environment will operate under well-defined conditions to ensure trust and safeguard the public interest.
European Research Area (ERA) ⁸	The European Research Area (ERA) is the ambition to create a single, borderless market for research, innovation and technology across the EU. By strongly aligning their research policies and programmes, European countries become more effective in the research sector. The ERA is based on excellence and prioritises investments and reforms in research and innovation, boosts market uptake, strengthens mobility of researchers and free flow of knowledge and technology, and improves access to excellence.

² <https://www.4ch-project.eu/what-is-a-competence-centre/>

³ <https://oscars-project.eu/clusters-open-science-competence-centres>

⁴ <https://www.esfri.eu/research-infrastructure-ri>

⁵ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/home.html>

⁶ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric_en

⁷ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

⁸ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-area_en

European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) ⁹	ESFRI, the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures, is a strategic instrument to develop the scientific integration of Europe and to strengthen its international outreach.
Digital Research Object	Definition: A digital object is 'an object composed of a set of bit sequences' (Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems - CCSDS, 2012). Digital Research Object is a digital object that is used and or produced in the context of research.
Composability ¹⁰	Definition: The quality of a system's components to be selected and assembled in various combinations. Example of use: OSCARS' CODAS are designed to be highly composable, allowing for tailored solutions to specific research needs.

⁹ <https://www.esfri.eu/about-esfri>

¹⁰ <https://oscars-project.eu/glossary>

Supplementary Material 3: Challenges and Solutions in Implementing Competence Centres (CCs) in Life Sciences (LS). This table presents the main challenges (4 votes and more) faced in establishing CCs in the LS domain, alongside proposed solutions. These have been categorised into three overarching areas: Foundational (related to scope), policy-related (covering sustainability and governance), and technical (addressing interoperability). The challenges and solutions were co-developed by authors representing the LS-RI community through a Radical Collaboration process. They were then prioritised via a structured voting process. The ten most critical challenges identified are discussed in more detail in the main text of the paper.

Area	Challenge	Proposed Solution(s)	Initials (vote)
Scope	Lack of consensus and clarity on the definition, requirements, and implementation of CCs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a shared vision of CC and its goals within the LS-RI communities through a series of participatory on-line workshops and present them in common papers (like this one) Consensus building exercises across decision makers in the LS-RIs and employment of tools to align different views (e.g., Delphi reviews, collaborative papers...) 	APM, KE, GS, MM, RM, MAR, RD, NL, ARy
	Low awareness and engagement with CCs among researchers within and outside existing RIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Socialising the concept of CCs through stakeholder engagement Community outreach (e.g., through training) to researchers outside of RIs Broaden the number of RIs that are connected to CCs so that each LS-RI is associated to CCs addressing challenges in the fields of its scope (or at least has the opportunity to do so) 	KE, ASB, GS, MM, RM, MAR, RD, NL, ARy, JT
Sustainability Source: https://www.embopress.org/doi/full/10.15252/emboj.2023115008	Ensuring long-term sustainability and investment in human and capital resources for CCs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Propose funding models and strategies for maintaining human and capital resources for CCs KPIs to monitor LS-RI CC activity to inform the need and potential options for sustainability Provide resources for training 	APM, KE, ASB, MM, RM, DD, RD, NL, ARy
	Incentives and funding are needed to support FAIR and Open Science practices for researchers and service owners/providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Encourage the use of DOIs and other well recognized PIDs for attribution of digital objects Advocate for the inclusion of data and software publications utilising ORCID Advocate for scientific Journal policies to promote or require peer-reviewed publications to have associated FAIR/Open datasets Ensure EC funding specifically for data management and FAIR/open practices Implement a reward system for contributions to CCs Develop badges of approval for repositories of data, software and biological material that meet high FAIR and quality standards and implement community standards (visible through indexation in catalogues e.g. FAIRsharing, Sansone et al., 2019) 	APM, KE, ASB, MM, RM, DD, RD, NL, ARy, JT
	Lack of funding and incentives for implementing EOSC recommendations and guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider integrating funding for the implementation of EOSC recommendations and guidelines into INFRA EOSC or establish a continuous, non-competitive funding stream. Clarify the regulatory framework that would support this approach. At the policy level, prioritise providing value to the target audience with minimal barrier adoption Ensure all calls for projects involving data generation and management explicitly address the need for FAIR & quality data handling and include dedicated funding for these requirements. 	RD, NL, ARy, RM

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate/promote/fund cooperation between actors 	
	Heterogeneous capacity within and across CC landscape, including knowledge and expertise in data lifecycle management, quality of data management, and quality of data/data services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular open workshops funded by CCs, targeted to CC staff and partners to increase community governance and harmonisation of LS inter RIs tools and methods for FAIR implementation (e.g. Papoutsoglou 2020, Ohmann et al., 2022, David et al., 2022, Soiland-Reyes et al., 2022) 	APM, MM, RM, RD
	<p>Lack of effective long-term sustainability (Ref) strategies for new resources and services for CCs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Risk of confusion with RIs' actions. Risk of losing progress if sustained support is not guaranteed Risk of losing expertise crucial for maintaining and developing tools and solutions Risk of limited recognition of FAIR skills and inappropriate actions for FAIR sharing of data, software and workflows 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CCs need clear, guaranteed support and a defined lifespan from the EC to ensure long-term viability and minimise resource expenditure CC funding should be complementary to and not competitive with RI funding Allocation of sufficient resources to allow for CCs to operate as well identifiable entities Innovation and maintenance in CCs could be in addition supported by thematic Open Calls for projects (Outcomes in EOSC-Life Open Calls (Ref) and OSCARS Open Calls provide strong examples) Financial or career recognition-based incentives for FAIR sharing of data, software, and workflows 	APM, KE, RD, NL
Governance	Proliferation of governance layers can distract from development of scientific services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Streamline governance processes within CCs Offer examples or guidelines to establish CC governance mechanisms Focus on scientific services development Avoid administrative burden of creating new governance models but rather promote simple self-governance models for CCs, while incorporating and connecting already existing infrastructures and operational frameworks 	ASB, MM, RM, RD, NL, ARy
Interoperability	Definition and adoption of harmonised software, tools, and procedures for full interoperability of FAIR data resources among all LS-RIs. Local adaptations required for software systems to ensure interoperability can be complex and resource-intensive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common standards and frameworks incrementation for software (see Barker et al., 2022, Chue Hong et al., 2022), tools, and procedures EOSC components, such as Task Forces¹¹, Opportunity Area experts groups¹² or other groups, can iteratively develop and refine Legal, Organisational, Semantic, and Technical (L-O-S-T) interoperability. Focussed funding and sharing of resources, technologies, lessons learned via a central online portal Identifying timely steps, potential synergies and sharing of procedures between different large-scale, data-driven projects and initiatives (central project registry could help and platform for regular exchange can help) 	APM, KE, ASB, MM, RM, RD, NL, ARy

¹¹ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-task-forces/>

¹² <https://eosc.eu/eosc-opportunity-area-expert-groups/>

	<p>Gaps in data stewardship between acquisition and publication that vary across RIs and CCs, including limited capacity and resources for FAIR data stewardship to individual scientists and users</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promote the Data Steward role/career, particularly in RIs, but also in every data generating organisation (eventually gain support in the EOSC SRIA). These professionals can bridge data CC/RI services with the R&I organisations, supporting/enlarging FAIR data exposure ● Create stronger links and exchange between data stewards through inter-RIs (or clusters) events / workshop, a data steward registry and commons for data stewardship in CCs, and EOSC related components (Task Force, Opportunity Action, and others) ● Introduce and sustain permanent positions for focussed data stewards missions including FAIR training activities 	<p>APM, KE, ASB, MM, RM, NL, ARy, RD</p>
	<p>Effective sharing, integration and quality control of data across diverse networks involves defining key steps, stakeholders, skills, and needs for data mobilisation assessment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Utilisation of tools such as playbooks (e.g., EFPIA's data sharing playbook) ● Designing inclusive data quality assessment principles 	<p>APM,ASB, RD, NL</p>
	<p>Storage solutions for large volumes of data are crucial for FAIR data management and need exploration</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Establishment of shared, harmonised clouds which are federated and technically distributed (EC, universities, European Medical Cloud - see Rujano MA, 2024) ● Funding stream for research organisations to purchase storage in return for making those data FAIR and as Open as possible ● Provide free or cheap temporary storage capacities for analysing data or preparing it for publication before the data moves to repositories 	<p>APM, KE,ASB, MM, RM, ARy, RD, NL</p>

Supplementary Material 4: Complementary Challenges in Implementing Competence Centres (CCs) in Life Sciences. This supplementary material includes challenges that were considered for the implementation of CCs in LS but were not retained among the ten highest-priority items presented in the main body of the paper. The entries include lower-priority challenges, which were fully formulated and evaluated but received fewer votes in the prioritisation process (Supplementary Material 3), and exploratory challenges, which emerged during the Radical Collaboration process but were not developed in full. This may be due to unclear articulation of the challenge of the absence of a corresponding solution at the time of analysis. These entries are shared for transparency and to reflect the broader scope of discussions within the LS-RI community during the development of this work.

Unclear Definition and Integration of CCs within EOSC Nodes

Complementary to Challenge 1: Definition and Consensus Building, a further obstacle could be the ambiguity surrounding the roles and interactions of CCs with emerging EOSC Nodes and Research Infrastructures (RIs). The lack of a unified vision on how CCs should function within the broader EOSC framework could lead to inconsistencies in governance and hinder collaboration. Addressing this requires discussing common solutions in participatory workshops with LS-RI members, EOSC governance bodies, and policymakers to establish clear operational guidelines and well-defined interactions for CCs. A structured categorisation of EOSC Nodes, with examples of successful integrations, would enhance their strategic role and impact.

The Scalability of CC Models Across Scientific Disciplines

Moreover, while **Challenge 1** emphasised the need for a shared CC vision, an additional consideration is the adaptability of CC models to different scientific disciplines. CC frameworks developed for LS-RIs may not seamlessly transfer to other domains such as physics, astronomy, environmental science, or social science and humanities. Ensuring CC models remain flexible and adaptable through modular implementation strategies would support cross-disciplinary scalability.

Awareness and Engagement Across Disciplines

Complementary to **Challenge 2: Awareness and Community Engagement**, another challenge lies in the difficulty of engaging researchers from traditionally less data-intensive disciplines, who may not immediately recognise the value of CCs. Encouraging the participation of a broader range of stakeholders through discipline-specific engagement strategies, tailored training, ambassador programmes to foster early adoption, and integration with national research initiatives would enhance CC adoption and usability. Furthermore, leveraging open-access platforms for knowledge dissemination and success stories would reinforce their value proposition across domains.

Complexity of Coordination Between RIs and Emerging Initiatives

Complementary to **Challenge 3: Governance Complexity**, the broader issue of coordination among RIs, including European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs), European Digital Infrastructure Consortia (EDICs), International Organisations (IOs), and newer initiatives such as the European Health Data Space (EHDS), remains unresolved. The varying historical and organisational structures of RIs result in different approaches to data management, standardisation, and interoperability, making cross-collaboration complex. Greater effort is needed to harmonise these approaches through inter-RI workshops and cross-domain governance initiatives that ensure alignment and avoid redundancy in CC functions.

Balance Between FAIR and Trusted Research Environments (TREs)

Complementary to **Challenge 4: Incentives for FAIR and Open Science**, FAIR data principles emphasise openness and reusability, yet many LS-RIs, particularly those dealing with sensitive health and personal data, require stringent access controls through Trusted Research Environments (TREs). Researchers often lack clear guidance on how to balance Open Science principles with legal and ethical constraints. CCs could play a pivotal role in educating researchers on implementing FAIR-compliant workflows within TREs, providing training and guidelines on secure data-sharing

models that respect privacy and ethical considerations.

Ethical and Legal Compliance Without Compromising Innovation

Complementary to **Challenge 5: Funding and Policy Alignment**, legal and ethical considerations, particularly in regulated fields like biomedical research, pose challenges to data sharing and CC interoperability. A consistent approach to regulatory compliance—facilitated through standardised legal frameworks—would help mitigate these issues. CCs can serve as advisory entities, providing up-to-date regulatory guidance and compliance tools that enable researchers to navigate these constraints effectively without stifling innovation.

Sustainability and Long-Term Funding Strategies

Complementary to Challenge 6: Sustainability and Resource Allocation, an additional challenge lies in ensuring that CCs do not become siloed entities competing for limited resources with RIs. Instead, their funding should be complementary to RI initiatives, enabling CCs to function as integral components rather than parallel structures. A viable solution is fostering complementary EC funding streams, exploring public-private partnerships, and incorporating CC functions into long-term national and European research strategies. Furthermore, recognition mechanisms for CC contributions—such as indexing services for CC-driven research tools, datasets, and software—could improve their sustainability by embedding their outputs into citation and funding assessment frameworks.

Cross-Domain and Cross-Cluster Synergies

Complementary to **Challenge 7: Interoperability and Standardisation**, there is currently no well-defined mechanism for fostering collaboration between CCs across different scientific clusters. While the FAIR principles and EOSC guidelines provide a common framework, targeted initiatives to promote inter-cluster partnerships are lacking. Establishing regular cross-cluster workshops and collaborative projects would maximise resource-sharing and prevent duplication of efforts. A structured mechanism for co-developing standards and best practices across domains would also strengthen interdisciplinary research outcomes.

Ensuring CC Integration with Emerging AI and Automation Technologies

Another key challenge related to **Challenge 7** is the integration of CCs with emerging Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven tools and automation technologies. AI and machine learning are increasingly used in data analysis and curation, but CCs currently lack structured strategies to incorporate these technologies into their frameworks. Establishing dedicated AI adoption roadmaps for CCs would ensure that automation enhances rather than complicates CC operations (see discussions in EOSC about [AI4FAIR](#) and [FAIR4AI](#)).

Enhancing Interoperability Beyond Technical Standards

Complementary to Challenge 8: Data Stewardship and Quality Control, interoperability challenges extend beyond technical considerations such as APIs and metadata standards. An identified key issue is the lack of uniform quality assessment frameworks for data and data management. While some domains, such as health sciences, are developing maturity labels and quality assessment models (e.g., EHDS's quality labels for health data), similar frameworks must be established for other LS-RIs. Community-driven tools, such as playbooks and assessment checklists, could provide standardised evaluation metrics that ensure interoperability beyond technical integration.

Long-Term Career Pathways for CC Personnel

Challenge 9: Heterogeneous Capacity and Skills Development focused on training, but a complementary issue is the long-term career sustainability of professionals working within CCs. Unlike traditional academic roles, CC-related positions currently lack clear career progression pathways, which might lead to talent attrition and low retention. Establishing professional development frameworks, including tenure-equivalent roles and skill recognition systems for CC professionals as proposed by the Skills4EOSC project, is necessary to sustain expertise within CCs.